

Brain-Derived Neurotrophic Factor – its unique role and future perspectives as a therapeutic target: A Literature Review

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Abstract

Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) is one of the key proteins involved in synaptic function, neuronal growth, and differentiation. The aim of this work is to present the latest reports in recent years on its function in selected diseases.

Keywords

BDNF, neuroplasticity, autism spectrum disorder, Alzheimer's disease, anorexia nervosa

Introduction

The proper functioning of both the central and peripheral nervous systems is closely linked to the family of neurotrophins, protein substances secreted by neurons. The function of these molecules is to maintain neuronal health, which is why they are called *neurotrophic factors*, derived from the Greek word *trophe*, meaning "to nourish" or "to feed" [1].

There are many neurotrophic factors whose properties have been the subject of interest of researchers worldwide for years. Their importance for brain nerve cells is extremely important, as they determine their survival, development, and regulation. The family of molecules that influence neuronal growth includes: NGF – nerve growth factor, BDNF - brain-derived neurotrophic factor and NT-3 and NT-4 - neurotrophin 3 and neurotrophin 4 [2].

Abnormal levels of BDNF expression are associated with numerous neurodegenerative and neuropsychiatric conditions. The field of neurobiology has become challenged by the search for clinical applications of the discovered properties of brain-derived neurotrophic factor. BDNF appears to be an important therapeutic target in the search for innovative approaches in medicine and the treatment of neurodegenerative and psychiatric diseases such as Alzheimer's disease, Parkinson's disease, brain tumors, depression, and PTSD (Post-traumatic stress disorder). According to the authors, the use of BDNF could be revolutionary as one of the key components of personalized medicine [3,4].

The aim of this paper is to present selected recent reports on the function of brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF). This review highlights the remarkable results of research on molecules involved in synaptic transmission, neurogenesis and neuromodulation, and the potential therapeutic benefits they may offer.

Materials and methods

A literature review has been conducted using databases such as PubMed, NCBI, and Google Scholar. The search process included using keywords such as "BDNF", "BDNF and autism", "neuroplasticity", "BDNF and anorexia nervosa", "BDNF and Alzheimer's disease", and "BDNF and glioblastoma" to identify relevant data. Data from the searched English-language articles were carefully analyzed for methodology, results, and relevance to the topic to ensure study credibility. Furthermore, only full-text studies published between 2000 and 2025 were used. Special attention was paid to the most recent years of publication.

BDNF - structure and physiology

BDNF is currently the best-known neurotrophic factor and has been recognized as the most universal and crucial element in maintaining healthy and balanced brain processes. BDNF was isolated from pig brain in 1982 and shown to promote the survival and differentiation of sensory neurons. Since then, the mechanisms of its gene regulation, expression, metabolic pathways, and the receptors through which it activates have been elucidated [5].

BDNF gene expression has been described in both physiological and pathological conditions. Expression levels of this neurotrophin are low at birth but increase rapidly during the first weeks of postnatal development. BDNF expression is abundant in the hippocampus, neocortex, amygdala, and cerebellum [6]. BDNF appears to strengthen excitatory (glutamatergic) synapses and weaken inhibitory (GABAergic) synapses [5].

The brain-derived neurotrophic factor gene is located on chromosome 11 and its structure is highly conserved among mammals. Transcription of the *Bdnf* gene is tightly regulated, cell type-specific, and controlled by neuronal activity. Disruption of the BDNF gene in mice has been shown to cause loss of some types of peripheral neurons but does not cause drastic changes in the central nervous system [7].

It has been demonstrated that there is a precursor form, pro-BDNF, and a mature form, m-BDNF. The precursor form of pro-BDNF is converted to m-BDNF by metalloproteinase-2 and metalloproteinase-9 (MMP2 and MMP9). Both forms are biologically active, and secretion into the extracellular space enables their physiological effects. The ratio of pro-BDNF to m-BDNF varies depending on the stage of brain development and its region. Among the most important functions of pro-BDNF are the promotion of apoptosis and its negative impact on neuronal remodeling, as manifested by disturbances in the shape and number of dendritic spines. M-BDNF supports the development of psychological processes related to neurogenesis and gliogenesis, dendritic growth, dendritic branching, and dendritic spine formation. The physiological function of m-BDNF is linked to improved developmental processes, as well as adult processes that require increased brain activity and support the efficient transmission of stimuli in the synaptic system, ultimately leading to improved memory and cognitive function. Appropriate BDNF activity prevents the death of neurons and brain cells and promotes the repair of damaged cells in the CNS. BDNF influences the neurogenesis of new neurons, enabling more efficient information flow between brain cells and improving the efficiency of cognitive processes [8,9].

There is compelling evidence that proBDNF and m-BDNF use different receptors to mediate opposing neuronal actions to regulate neuronal excitability, neuronal remodeling, synaptic communication, and plasticity in the central nervous system. While m-BDNF has the ability to increase neuronal excitability and synaptic strength, pro-BDNF can decrease neuronal excitability, reduce synaptic efficiency, and facilitate synaptic weakening [7]. Low BDNF activity reduces the activity and functionality of synapses and neurons. Reduced brain-derived neurotrophic factor has been linked to conditions such as cellular aging, Alzheimer's disease, depression and schizophrenia [3,10].

BDNF acts through different receptors depending on the isoform. M-BDNF acts on Trk receptors with tropomyosin B kinase activity, while pro-BDNF acts on the p75NTR receptor, a member of the tumor necrosis factor receptor (TNFR) family, which is important in apoptosis and programmed cell death. These receptors have been found in the hippocampus, the granular layer of the cerebellar cortex, and the frontal lobes of the cerebral cortex. The mutual balance and interaction between Trk receptors, as well as interaction with the p75NTR receptor, determines proper neurogenesis and the balance between neurogenesis and neurodegeneration. It has been proven that BDNF binding to TrkB is essential for BDNF's

action in modulating the synaptogenesis process, leads to the maturation of nerve cells and participates in neuronal plasticity [2,11,12].

The development of the brain requires coordinated processes of neuroplasticity and gliogenesis, the formation of neurons and synapses, and the elimination of erroneous synapses formed through cell death mechanisms. Neuroplasticity is the ability to reorganize the structure, function and connections between neurons in response to intracellular and extracellular factors. In animal models, mice deprived of BDNF have been observed to die within the second week after birth [13].

BDNF, through its role in signaling between neurons, is a key regulator of synaptic plasticity. Research on synaptic plasticity has led to the creation of two cellular models: LTP (*long-term potentiation*) and LTD (*long-term depression*), which illustrate changes in the morphological properties of neuronal dendritic spines and their plasticity under the influence of changing external and internal conditions [7].

Animal models have implicated BDNF in functions such as learning, memory, cognition, perception, and emotion regulation. Furthermore, in humans, BDNF and TrkB signaling have been implicated in numerous psychiatric disorders and are therefore widely studied in the context of schizophrenia, child autism, depression, addiction, and anxiety disorders [14]. In addition to its neurotrophic properties, BDNF has also been shown to act on blood vessels and promote neoangiogenesis in ischemic tissues [15].

BDNF in neurological diseases

Alzheimer's disease, Huntington's disease, and amyotrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS) are diseases where the key pathogenetic mechanism is the death of nerve cells. These diseases are chronic, leading to significant disability, and are a huge burden for both patients and their families, as well as society.

According to data, 70% of dementias are caused by Alzheimer's disease. It seems that BDNF may play an important role in neurodegenerative processes due to its neuroprotective function [10,13]. For several years, scientists have been trying to use the potential of molecules from the neurotrophin family in gene therapy for people suffering from neurodegenerative diseases. The first studies have yielded promising results. All patients tested showed a response characterized by the formation of new axons. Responses to the neurotrophin NGF persisted for up to ten years after gene transfer. Subgroups of patients examined for neuronal hypertrophy and activation provide additional evidence of trophic activity. Importantly, no adverse pathological effects were observed during this period [16]. In 2020, scientists from San Diego began the world's first trials of using BDNF. Currently, the first phase of clinical trials is underway on 12 participants, in which adenoviral vector (AAV) gene therapy is being conducted to slow or prevent neuronal loss in people with Alzheimer's disease or mild cognitive impairment (MCI). It is worth noting that gene therapy is being used because BDNF does not cross the blood-brain barrier (BBB) [17].

BDNF in brain cancer

Neurotrophins, as growth factors, are involved in cell-dependent mechanisms that promote proliferation, enhance anti-apoptosis signaling, and render cells unresponsive to antiproliferative stimuli. The role of BDNF in brain tumors appears to be an extremely interesting finding. Furthermore, high levels of BDNF have been found in neuroblastoma cells, which have been associated with a better prognosis for this tumor [18]. BDNF has been shown to stimulate IL-15 production by mouse microglia, which in response stimulated NK cells to produce IFN- γ , influencing the myeloid cell phenotype, shifting them toward an antitumor state and oncolytic activity [13,19]. The use of BDNF as a potential marker of glioma, especially in classifying its degree of malignancy, has also become the subject of research by scientists [20].

BNDF in anorexia nervosa

Anorexia nervosa is a psychiatric illness with the highest mortality rate. The underlying pathogenic processes are still unclear, which is why neurotrophins have become a focus of research in the context of anorexia nervosa. BDNF is undoubtedly involved in the regulatory processes that maintain body weight and eating habits. Studies have shown that BDNF levels in individuals with anorexia nervosa are reduced compared to healthy controls and increase during recovery [21]. It is known that atrophy of the gray and white cortex is observed during long-term illness, and malnutrition may particularly affect the structure and function of brain regions associated with high metabolic rates, such as the hippocampus, where neurogenesis continues throughout life. Studies suggest that BDNF levels could be a marker of clinical improvement in patients with anorexia nervosa. Moreover, an increase in BDNF concentration improves neuroplasticity and cognitive functions, which facilitates the treatment process, especially in the field of psychotherapy [22,23].

BNDF in autism spectrum disorders

Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) is becoming one of the most prevalent and simultaneously most enigmatic disorders in child psychiatry. Epidemiological data indicate that the number of children diagnosed with this disorder is steadily increasing, with boys being diagnosed significantly more often than girls. Clinical symptoms vary among patients, but the basis for diagnosis is impaired social skills, repetitive behavioral patterns, and inappropriate sensory responses. Deficiencies in empathy, poor vocabulary, and difficulty maintaining eye contact have been suggested. To date, no clear cause has been identified [24]. Studies have shown that BDNF levels can both decrease and increase in patients with autism spectrum disorder. Scientists believe that BDNF plays a key role in neurodevelopmental processes, and its variable levels explain the abnormal connectivity of neural pathways in ASD patients. BDNF levels have been found to correlate with a greater severity of all core behavioral symptoms of ASD [25]. This is a question that researchers are asking themselves when considering the potential clinical applications of BDNF. It is suggested that this neurotrophin could be used as

a diagnostic tool for ASD. It is emphasized that there is currently no standardized, sensitive testing method, but if further research yields the ability to measure BDNF in accordance with laboratory test standards, it could be a marker in newborns for early identification of autism spectrum disorders and the earliest possible therapeutic intervention [26]. However, it should be noted that differences in BDNF levels are also observed in children with mental retardation [27]. Interesting reports have been obtained by scientists examining the correlations between BDNF concentrations and omega-3 fatty acids. Regular supplementation of these acids has been shown to reduce BDNF levels, so it seems that it may have a protective effect on synaptic dysfunctions [28]. Aerobic exercise has been shown in animal models to increase BDNF concentration in the hippocampus, suggesting the potential of using such training in individuals with ASD to support neural plasticity [29].

BDNF and factors modulating neurogenesis

Fluctuations in BDNF levels may result not only from the disease state of the patients studied but also depend on many factors: diet, hormone levels, physical activity, cigarette smoking, and stress levels. Studies by many authors confirm the influence of these factors on BDNF levels [30,31,32]. Other reports emphasize the influence of somatic diseases on BDNF levels in peripheral blood, particularly cardiovascular diseases, hormonal disorders, and metabolic syndrome [33,34,35].

Physical activity has been shown to have a beneficial effect on neuronal plasticity and BDNF levels. In patients with depression, levels of this neurotrophin were monitored and increased in the hippocampus during physical exercise, particularly aerobic exercise. This suggests the potential for improved cognitive function, memory, and learning [13,31,33].

The optimal environment for improving cognitive function, achieved through increased BDNF, also includes adequate sleep and proper regeneration. Stress levels are equally important, as they lower BDNF levels and influence neurogenesis [36].

Additionally, it's worth mentioning reports regarding diet. Researchers found that consuming berries or green tea, rich in neuroprotective flavonoids and polyphenols, as well as spices such as curcumin, for 12 weeks in older adults significantly increased BDNF levels and improved memory and cognitive function [3,30,37].

Limitations and difficulties

There is no doubt that efforts should be made to identify potential clinical applications for BDNF. However, researchers have pointed out that drugs that mimic BDNF or therapies that inhibit or enhance TrkB signaling may lead to uncontrolled growth effects, such as tumor growth or cancer cell migration, seizures, or excitotoxicity - the undesirable stimulation of long-term changes in synaptic plasticity that could lead to mechanisms underlying addiction. It is also worth recalling that BDNF has poor ability to cross the blood-brain barrier, which may also pose a challenge in attempts to use it therapeutically [4,7].

Conclusions

Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) possesses remarkable properties that could provide the basis for a unique application in the treatment of both neurological and psychiatric diseases. Due to its crucial role in neurogenesis, synaptic plasticity, and neuronal cell health, BDNF is crucial for proper brain function. Therefore, it has been extensively studied in relation to neurological and psychiatric disorders associated with abnormal brain development and function. It is clear that BDNF plays a significant role in the pathophysiology of disorders such as brain tumors, Alzheimer's disease, autism, and eating disorders. However, further research will be necessary to determine whether BDNF is a risk factor for the initiation, maintenance, or recovery of each of these distinct disorders and what impact its function has at the peripheral level at each of these stages. Furthermore, the search for more effective BDNF-based therapies is crucial given the impact BDNF has on these disease processes. The future of BDNF is certainly the center of interest for researchers, but we can now operate at the level of knowledge we know and support neuroplasticity in both healthy people and those struggling with psychiatric and neurological conditions.

Disclosures and Declarations

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